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“If I had wanted to become an educator, I would have studied it.”¹ Career changers into VET teaching and the implications for the VET teaching profession in Germany

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Abstract

In Berlin, many career changers teach in VET schools. This article highlights some of the results of an explorative interview study with career changers. Three types of career changers can be distinguished. All types of career changers tend to devalue pedagogy and share an economic understanding of VET schools.

Keywords

VET teacher; career changers; teaching profession

1. Introduction

There is a huge lack of teachers in Germany, that also concerns VET schools (Frommberger & Lange, 2018). To meet this shortage many academics from other fields are being encouraged to start a new career as a teacher.

In general people studying to become a teacher do a bachelor and a master that includes their two subjects, teaching methodology and educational sciences at university before starting their internship that takes 18 months and that is accompanied by the senate administration for education. In the end they complete with a state examination. In subjects that lack teachers, graduates of that subject can directly start with their internship. During their internship they already teach 19 lessons per week – without any preparation². Almost all VET subjects lack teachers at the moment.

In the school year 2017/2018 22.3% of the new teachers at VET schools were career changers (Senatsverwaltung, 2018). Although this is a considerable number there is very little knowledge about the situation and the different backgrounds of these teachers who did not attend university's teacher training. To put it in the words of Tenberg: They are the “stepchildren” of VET teaching (Tenberg, 2015).

In this small explorative study, we wanted to know how career changers at VET schools in Berlin perceive their situation. What is their understanding of professional teaching and does this have implications for the professionalisation of VET teachers in general? Is there a danger to undermine the classic path towards VET teaching which seems to be cause for concern especially for representatives of the university teacher training (Frommberger & Lange,

¹ Wenn ich Pädagogin hätte werden wollen, hätte ich das studiert.“ Quotation from an interview

² The senate administration for education, youth and family recently introduced a 7 day course to prepare career changers for teaching.

2018; Tenberg, 2015)? On the other hand, we wanted to know; Who are these career changers? As there is an ongoing lack of teachers it might be helpful to know something about them in terms of educational aspects of recruitment.

2. Methodical Approach

Although there are many career changers in German VET schools, there is surprisingly little research. There are few studies on school management (Faßhauer & Jersak, 2013; Tenberg, 2015) but as far as we know, there are no studies focussing on the career changers themselves.

In the present study, we interviewed nine career changers. They all have degrees in a technical discipline and work now as teachers at a VET school in Berlin. They were about to start their internship or have successfully completed it in the past. Access to them was realised through the school managements. The interviews were analysed by the team of our department, Prof. Dr. Kirsten Lehmkuhl, Dr. Marcus Eckelt and me, based on Grounded Theory (Glaser & Strauss, 2005 [1967]; Strauss & Corbin, 1996). To validate our results, we did an expert interview with a director of the internship.

3. Results

3.1. Types of career changers into VET Teaching

In our analysis we found three different types of career changers that differ in their professional biography but also in other dimensions.

3.1.1. Younger Beginner

This type is not only younger than the others but has also done a vocational training in the field where they now work as a teacher. They have studied at a university for applied sciences before becoming a teacher.

The internship with its seminars, the pedagogical culture and the academic habitus seem to be a challenge for this type. However, they highlight the proximity and familiarity with the pupils. In terms of social class relations, this type clearly experienced social advancement. As a teacher there is a relatively high and secure income plus a comparatively high prestige. On the other hand that type does not have to change the own manners and can still be around the pupils that mainly represent working class. So, one could say that type manages to arrange the advantages of both social classes.

3.1.2. Older Changer

After the studying engineering this type has worked a while in private enterprises. Often, they started a business. They were suffering from precarious situations and hence decided to change. This type is especially looking for financial security and planning capability that an employment as teacher offers.

The older changer emphasises their experiences in the labour market and entrepreneurial spirit and considers this as the advantage for teaching in VET schools.

Talking about students, this type tends to take a parental perspective.

This type was quite multifarious in our analysis. In future studies it might be worth considering subcategories.

3.1.3. Academic Dropout

This type of career changers did their doctorate and did research and teaching at university. Due to the unattractive working conditions for non-professorial teaching staff at university, which only offer temporary employment, the academic dropout is also looking for planning

capability. This type feels familiar with the contents and the habitus of the internship and also talks about good relations to the school management.

The VET system and the students are a terra incognita to them. They tend to be actively distanced from their students.

In the academic hierarchy, a person with a PhD is above a Master of Education. Therefore this type accepts a social decline in exchange for financial security and planning capability.

3.2. Two thesis on the implications for VET schools in Berlin

Although the career changers differ in several aspects, there are some topics running through all the interviews.

3.2.1. *Career Changers tend to devalue pedagogy*

With a background in engineering/natural sciences and experiences in enterprises, career changers often refer to their knowledge as more significant than a solid teacher training. They do not recognise pedagogy as an actual academic discipline. In this perspective, professionalism is not based on being aware of the antinomies in teaching practises and reflecting them (Helsper, 2004). The quotation in the title „If I had wanted to become an educator, I would have studied it.” reflects a self-conception as VET teacher, that does not include pedagogy as an important component.

There are also some indicators that the career changers have not a precise concept of what teaching methodology is. Amongst career changers, the request for recipes and clear guidelines seems to be high.

3.2.2. *Career Changers abet an economic understanding of VET schools*

Career changers talk about schools in economic terms. They describe schools as enterprises with a reform bottleneck. And they present themselves as high performance employees in contrast to their colleagues who think, discuss and reflect too much and therefore cannot achieve as much as they do. Furthermore students are often referred to as clients.

The comprehension of market economy as the standard of comparison for schools conflicts with the ethos of the pedagogical profession (Radtke, 2006). Humanist ideals like empowering the less privileged or enhance social justice cannot be found in the interviews.

This understanding of professionalism coincides with the concept of New Professionalism. In this model of teaching professionalism, the emphasises lies on customer orientation, efficiency, quality management and competition. Research in Great Britain has also shown that this concept is quite popular among career changers (Terhart, 2011).

4. Concluding remarks

The question arises how the quantitatively large presence of career changers has a long-term effect on VET schools. For this purpose, further investigations are required in order to examine the here presented types in more detail.

In this explorative study we found career changers who report about satisfaction in their new career. As Berlin is recruiting an increasing number of career changers, this is one important finding: Engineers and natural scientists can become pleased VET teachers.

We found different three types of career changers. A better knowledge of them and their perspective is necessary to adapt the internship adequately and reflect these differences. How can the distance between career changers and their pupils on one hand and the distance between career changers and their colleagues and school management on the other hand be reduced?

In terms of recruitment it might be of interest, that financial security and planning capability are the main motives for a career change. Although we know, that initial career satisfaction correlates with altruistic motivations (Watt, 2012), these pragmatic motivations dominated our interviews.

Considering the implications for the VET teaching profession we can observe some challenges.

Because of the enormous lack of VET teachers, the way for career changers is getting easier - sometimes even easier than the classic way of becoming a VET teacher. What will be the long-term consequences?

In the end, career changers bring up the question: What are VET schools there for? Is it only about knowledge transfer and prepare students for the labour market? Or is there an educational mission that reaches beyond that?

Since there is no end to the shortage of VET teachers, the training of career changers should be made evidence-based, so as not to forego pedagogical professionalism in favour of a quick compensation for the lack of teachers.

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Biographical notes

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